

Determination of Stability Constant of Cobalt(II) Acetyl Acetate Using Solvent Extraction

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From the distribution of cobalt(II) acetyl acetate in different diluents, the composition of the extractable complexes and the extraction constants were calculated. The results indicate that acetyl acetone forms complexes with Co(II) of the type $[\text{Co}(\text{AcAc})_2]_4$, which is a tetramer.

ACETYL acetone is one of the best organic reagents which forms extractable chelates with many metals^{1,2}. It serves as both extraction solvent and complexing agent in extraction of metals from aqueous solutions. In aqueous solutions, it acts as a weak acid ($\text{P}k_a=8.9$). The extraction behaviour of Co-acetyl acetate with isobutyl alcohol, cyclohexanone^{3,4} and benzene was studied. The maximum extraction was reached in the above cases at different pH values.

The present work involves the use of solvent extraction technique to investigate the nature and stability of the products formed during the extraction of cobalt acetyl acetate $\text{Co}(\text{AcAc})_2$ in different solvents at pH 2-7. Very few authors have studied the stability of metal acetyl acetate formed in solvent extraction⁵. The stability of $\text{Co}(\text{AcAc})_2$ has been studied only potentiometrically in alcoholic medium⁷. So we have studied the optimum conditions for extraction of $\text{Co}(\text{AcAc})_2$ using solvents such as CCl_4 , CHCl_3 , *n*-hexane, ethyl acetate, toluene and xylene. The stability constant was compared with that found potentiometrically. The structure of the complex has also been investigated.

Experimental

Reagents :

All chemicals used were of A.R. and B.D.H. quality. Acetyl acetone (AcAc) was used after purification as mentioned by Pribil⁸.

Procedure :

Five mls. of the organic diluent containing 0.1M acetyl acetone were shaken in a mechanical shaker with an equal volume of aqueous solution containing the hydrous cobalt salt COX_2 (where $\text{X}=\text{Cl}^-$, NO_3^- and ClO_4^-) of known molarity. The pH was adjusted by the addition of an acetate buffer. The two layers were shaken until equilibrium is reached (4-10 hours depending on the diluent used). The

two layers separated and Co^{3+} determined complexometrically in the aqueous layer.

Results and Discussion

To maximise the extraction of Co(II) by AcAc in different diluents, several parameters have been tested such as : metal concentration, time of shaking and type of anions of cobalt salt. The ligand concentrations cannot be determined here since it requires lower concentration than 0.1M which with cobalt cannot be determined complexometrically but by radioisotope which was done in a previous paper⁹.

The distribution of Co(II) by 0.1 M AcAc in different solvents is shown in Fig. 1. The distribution

Fig. 1. Effect of pH on the distribution ratio (D) of Co(II) acetyl acetate in different diluents.

ratio D increases with all diluents used. At pH values lower than 3, the extraction was almost nil. However, above pH 3 the distribution ratio increases gradually till it reaches a maximum at pH 5.

Effect of Co^{2+} ion Concentration on Extraction :

The concentration range of cobalt ion at which polynuclear complexes hydrolysis products or polymeric form could occur, can be easily established using the distribution method. This can be achieved by studying the dependence of distribution ratio on the metal ion concentration in the aqueous phase keeping other variables constant.

It is quite clear from the distribution curve that the dependence of % E on the cobalt ion concentration in the aqueous phase decrease with increase of cobalt concentration in a more or less linear form (Fig. 2). This might indicate the possible formation of polymeric form of $Co(AcAc)_2$ in these diluents.

Fig. 2. Effect of $[Co]$ on the distribution ratio using n -hexane and amyl acetate as diluents.

Effect of Time of Shaking on Equilibrium for Extraction of $(AcAc)_2$:

The hydrated coordinatively unsaturated chelates are normally poorly extracted and therefore they require a long time of shaking to reach equilibrium because their rate of diffusion on extraction would be very slow. The time of equilibrium ranges from 2 to 10 hours depending on the diluent used.

Effect of Anions of Cobaltous Salt on Extraction :

To study the effect of anions on the per cent extraction of $Co(AcAc)_2$, different cobaltous salts

namely the chloride, nitrate and perchlorate were used, keeping Co^{2+} constant ($1 \times 10^{-3} M$) at pH_{max} . This was tried for three diluents which are amyl acetate, ethyl acetate and chloroform. The results show that the extraction of $Co(AcAc)_2$ is not affected by the type of anions used and this may be due to the fact that the stability of chloride, nitrate and perchlorate of $Co(II)$ are nearly the same in aqueous solution.

Calculation of Stability Constant of $Co(II)$ Acetyl Acetonate in Different Diluents :

To calculate the two-phase stability constant ($K_n D_n$ or B_n) of $Co(AcAc)_2$ where K_n and D_n are the stability constant and distribution coefficient of cobalt complex respectively, the different values of the dissociation constant of $AcAc$ (K_{AcAc}) and its distribution coefficient (q_{AcAc}) in the diluents were employed¹⁰. The distribution ratio D_o of $AcAc$ complex is given by¹¹

$$D_o = K_o \frac{[HA]_o^n}{[H]^n}$$

where K_o (the extraction constant) is equal to

$$K_o = \frac{[MA_n][HA_r]_o[H]^n}{[M^n][HA]_o^{n+r}} \dots \dots (i)$$

Subscript o denotes organic layer, r : change of chelating agent, n : charge on metal ion, MA_n : metal complex, HA : chelating acid.

A plot of $\log D_o$ vs pH at constant HA_o as shown in Fig. 3. gives a straight line of slope n^* and intercept ($\log K_o + n^* \log (HA)_o$). This indicates the formation of hydrated coordinating unsaturated chelate. At constant ligand concentration of the organic phase and different pH values using different diluents K_o is calculated from the following equation:

$$\log K_o = \log D_o - n^*[pH + \log [HA]_o] \dots \dots (ii)$$

Thus at each pH we have a value for K_o . The highest value of K_o is used to evaluate the stability constant ($K_n D_n$) by applying the following equation:

$$\log K_o = \log K_n D_n - n^* (\log q_{AcAc} + pK_{AcAc}) \dots (iii)$$

The higher the stability constant ($K_n D_n$) of the metal chelates HA_n , the higher will be K_o .

The value of n^* was expected to be 2- $Co(AcAc)_2$ extract as monomer, but here all the values of n^* obtained are less than 2; this is attributed to the formation of polymeric species.

Fig. 3. Relation between $\log D$ and pH for determination of n at constant $\log [HA]$

Results of calculations of $K_n D_n$ of $Co(AcAc)_2$ in different diluents are given in the following table :

Diluent	n^*	$\log K_n D_n$	Surface tension	Dielectric constant
Xylene	0.8	4.32	28.0	2.4
$CHCl_3$	0.44	2.44	27.1	5.1
<i>n</i> -Hexane	0.4	1.79	18.4	1.9
CCl_4	0.36	1.69	26.0	2.2

By comparing the values obtained for the stability constant of $Co(AcAc)_2$ using solvent extraction technique with those found potentiometrically, we conclude that they are very close together. Using the glass electrode⁷ at ionic strength 0.383 $K_n D_n = 4.73$, and at ionic strength 0.256 $K_n D_n = 4.96$ while in xylene at ionic strength 0.2M $K_n D_n = 4.32$.

From the above table, it is clear that the stability constant varies from one diluent to another and decreases with decreasing the surface tension of diluent with the exception of *n*-hexane and this may be due to the miscible effect.

Relation between $\log D_o$ and $\log K_o$:

Stary *et al*^{12,13} pointed out that a relationship exists between the distribution constant of a chelating agent (HA) and its uncharged metal chelate MA_n when the organic diluent is an inert molecule

such as CCl_4 , $CHCl_3$, *n*-hexane toluene or xylene. This relationship is extensively considered by Stary¹⁴ and Zolotov¹⁵. However the latter author has shown that there are some instances where this relationship is not obeyed.

This relation can be represented as :

$$\log K_o = N \log D_o + C$$

where C is a constant characteristic of the metal chelate and is given by :

$$C = N \log \frac{\text{molar volume of } MA_n}{\text{molar volume HA}} \dots \dots (iv)$$

and N is the number of aggregates of HA in the complex in the organic layer. Applying equation (iv) to cobalt-acetyl acetone in the different diluents used, a straight line (Fig. 4) with a value of $N = 7.65$.

Fig. 4. Relation between $\log D_o$ and $\log K_o$ (Determination of number of ligand molecules in Cobalt acetylacetone complex).

Since cobalt ion takes 2 molecules of AcAc to form the complex $Co(AcAc)_2$.

$$\text{then } N = \frac{7.65}{3} - 4$$

It is suggested, therefore, that cobalt acetyl acetate complex would have the general formula $Co(AcAc)_2$.

This result is in close agreement with that obtained by Fackler *et al*¹⁶ using the cryoscopic method.

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